

The Pervasiveness of Zionist Ideology within International Academia

Shahrazad Odeh

Shahrazad Odeh is a PhD student at Queen Mary, University of London. She is a human rights lawyer and researcher of law and gender. Email: s.odeh@qmul.ac.uk.

Since October 7th, Israeli universities have aligned themselves with Zionist values over the principle of academic freedom, choosing to prioritize their contribution to the country's ongoing war efforts. In doing so, they have suspended academic operations, shifted focus towards aiding national objectives, and actively recruited students for roles beyond academia (Odeh 2024).

This shift is manifested in various university actions, such as encouraging medical students to work in hospitals, offering them the chance to count their efforts towards civil or military service (Ghert-Zand 2023). Similarly, fashion schools have been co-opted into the war effort by mobilizing students to design and produce clothes with special pockets tailored to carry weapons (Stienberg 2023). This militarization of academic spaces extends beyond practical support for the war, as universities have also used their platforms to solicit students for Israel's hasbara (propaganda) efforts, encouraging them to spy on Palestinian students and report any "problematic" statements or behaviours (Odeh 2024). This collective reorientation has had significant ramifications for Palestinian students, many of whom have faced arrest or suspension, with some faculty members complicit in singling out individuals for actions as

innocuous as sharing Qur'anic verses, expressing a humanizing image of Gazans or participating in symbolic acts of cultural resistance (Arab Students of Bezalel Academy 2024).

This shift from academic freedom to nationalist participation is emblematic of a larger trend within Israeli academia, which has effectively become an arm of the state's political and military apparatus (Wind 2024). Palestinian students have been targeted en masse, often at the behest of their own professors and peers, reinforcing a climate of surveillance and repression. The arrests of hundreds of Palestinian students in the early months of the war—many of whom were detained for expressions of identity or dissent—reflect a systematic effort to suppress opposition and silence voices of resistance (Adalah 2023). These actions stand in stark contrast to the liberties afforded to Israeli students, some of whom have been permitted to carry weapons on campus or even harass their Palestinian counterparts, and even violently attack them in their dorm rooms and university premises — with impunity (Farah 2023). The discrepancy in treatment underscores the extent to which Israeli universities are privileging Zionist interests and undermining the very tenets of academic freedom.

Not only are Palestinian students being arrested and silenced, but the repression has extended to academic staff, including those of significant standing. The case of Nadera Shalhoub-Kevorkian, a renowned Palestinian scholar at the Hebrew University of Jerusalem, is a stark example of how academic freedom has been compromised in the name of Zionist interests (Odeh 2024). Despite her international acclaim, Shalhoub-Kevorkian has faced relentless attempts by her academic institute to discredit her work and silence her voice. With the onset of the war, the Hebrew University took increasingly severe measures to curtail her academic freedom, engaging in public campaigns to undermine her credibility, while taking procedural actions within the university to end her employment. This campaign against her culminated in her arrest and prosecution in April 2024 (Odeh 2024; Noy 2024), a move that sent a clear message to Palestinian academics: dissent will not be tolerated.

Shalhoub-Kevorkian's case highlights the precarious position of Palestinian academics within Israeli universities, where even tenured professors can be subjected to state-sanctioned repression. The complicity of her colleagues—many of whom had worked alongside her for years—demonstrates the pervasiveness of Zionist ideology within Israeli academia. Those who might have supported her were either silenced or unable to mount an effective defense, further illustrating the extent to which academic spaces in Israel are being transformed into platforms for Zionist nationalism only. The university's decision to force her out is a clear indication that there is little room for academic freedom that challenges the prevailing political order.

Yet even as they participate in the repression of Palestinian voices, Israeli universities

continue to market themselves as diverse and inclusive institutions. Palestinian students, often photographed and featured in university brochures, are used to project an image of multiculturalism and inclusivity (Odeh 2024). However, this image is a façade, masking the deeper reality of exclusion and oppression. The attack on Shalhoub-Kevorkian and the broader repression of Palestinian students expose the contradiction at the heart of Israeli academia: while it purports to uphold the values of free expression and academic inquiry, it simultaneously functions as a key player in the Zionist agenda (Wind 2024).

For Palestinian students and scholars, this means there is no escaping the Zionist framework that dictates the terms of their existence within these institutions. The persecution of Shalhoub-Kevorkian and other Palestinian students and academics is part of a broader effort to assert Zionist dominance within academia and to send a clear message: there is no place for radical Palestinian thought within these institutions (Wind 2024).

The repression of Palestinian voices within Israeli universities mirrors the suppression of pro-Palestinian movements on campuses worldwide. In the wake of the war, universities across the United States, the United Kingdom, and other countries have cracked down on pro-Palestinian activism, arresting thousands of students and staff for their participation in protests and encampments. In the United States alone, over 3,000 students have been arrested for resisting pro-Israel policies on campus (The New York Times 2024), similar arrests have occurred in the UK concluding the last academic year with about 1000 arrests of pro-Palestinian activists on UK campuses (Nagesh and McSorley 2024). Universities have also taken legal action against their own students, filing lawsuits to

suppress protests and encampments.

Similar to their Israeli counterparts, western universities continue to market themselves as diverse and inclusive institutions even as they participate in the repression of pro-Palestinian voices. They continue to profit from the knowledge produced by indigenous voices and scholars of critical theory—those who faced the toughest crackdown and punishment. They publish books and fund projects that purport to address issues such as colonialism, state violence, and inequality. However, these institutions' willingness to repress pro-Palestinian voices underscores the disconnect between their theoretical commitments and their actual practices. They capitalize on the intellectual contributions of marginalized voices while simultaneously silencing those who challenge the status quo.

The contradiction between theory and practice within universities—especially western academia—has become particularly stark in the context of the expanding genocide in Gaza. They design courses to raise awareness on the ongoing state violence in Israel but remain silent when their Palestinian alumni and students in Gaza face arrest, violence, and death.

In this context, Palestinian students and scholars are left with little recourse. Despite the solidarity of many of their peers, they find themselves without an academic home—excluded from spaces that purport to welcome them, punished for asserting their right to exist, and silenced for expressing dissent. This systemic exclusion demonstrates that, within western academia, there is no space for Palestinian voices to thrive, as the institutions designed to foster free inquiry and debate have instead become tools of repression and control.

In conclusion, both Israeli and Western academia serve as key instruments in upholding broader political and ideological frameworks of power and control. Israeli universities have become extensions of the state's Zionist objectives, sacrificing academic freedom in favour of nationalist agendas that target Palestinian students and scholars. This parallels the suppression occurring within Western universities, where Palestinian narratives are similarly marginalized. At first glance, the silencing of these voices may seem like a malfunction in systems that ostensibly champion freedom of speech, diversity, and human rights (Berlant 2016). However, this suppression is not an anomaly but a feature of the system itself. The marginalization of Palestinian perspectives in Western academia reflects the broader dynamics of Western sovereignty and domination, aligning with Noura Erekat's analysis in *Justice for Some*, which demonstrates how international legal systems are designed to maintain power imbalances favouring Western interests (Erekat 2019). While Western academia presents itself as a space for diversity and inclusion, it actively silences pro-Palestinian activism, exposing a profound hypocrisy between its stated values and actual practices. These institutions, whether in Israel or the West, are far from neutral; they are deeply implicated in sustaining hegemonic structures that suppress dissent and uphold systemic inequalities, ultimately reinforcing Western dominance. ♦

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